

Comparative Study on Time Management Skill and Decision-Making Skill in Youth and Sport Offices of Mekelle and Central Zones in Tigray Regional State

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Abstract

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The purpose of this study was to compare the time management skill and decision-making skill in the youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central Zones. This study includes both the governmental and nongovernmental bodies. Comparative survey specifically, Cross-sectional design was used to compare the four groups means Mekelle and Central Zone governmental and non-governmental bodies each other. The researcher used simple random sampling technique to select ten Woredas and Sub city youth and sport offices from the -19- Woredas and Sub-cities of the two Zones. The researcher also used purposive sampling technique to select the whole population (108) of the selected Woredas youth and sport offices as a respondent. A total of -23- self-made but standardized 5 liker test questionnaire and 5 unstructured interviews were used in order to collect concrete and relevant information about the above two variables. Pilot study was conducted to check the reliability of the questionnaires and the result of the test of reliability Alpha coefficient was 0.642 and 0 .845 for time management skill and decision-making skill respectively. One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to compare the time management skill and decision-making skills of youth and sport offices of Mekelle and central zone among the governmental and non-governmental bodies. Post-Hoc LSD multiple comparison was applied to identify the differences between the various groups in the youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central zone. The results obtained through post hoc multiple comparisons proved that, there were statistically significance difference among the governmental and non-governmental bodies in youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central Zones on their time management skill and decision-making skill.

INTRODUCTION

Time management is not distinct and separable from management in general and its aim is to prevent dawdling and waste of time and regulate working time. This management emphasizes on preventing unnecessary activities, increase of efficiency,

organizing and delegating tasks, Sport organizations are not exceptional to this. Time management for employees of sport organizations is the result of balance between time of sport, personal and occupational life. They should employ (a) prioritization of duties, (b) planning, organizing and

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evaluation of activities, (c) identification of the strategies for improving time management and (d) stress management to achieve time productivity. As a public organization, Sport and Youth offices plays a great role in planning and developing sport in cities and towns and serves as part of a social organ which continuously acts for supplying sport goals in one or several sport fields (Championship, public, professional, etc.). These directorates and offices are constituted from individuals and groups which purposefully collaborate with each other to fulfill the objectives of organization. The responsibility of the organizations' managers requires their function in the offices to be both effective and productive; although efficiency is very significant, effectiveness is critical and necessary (Mehdi *et al.*, 2014). Decision making is the study of identifying and choosing alternatives based on the values and preferences of the decision maker. Making a decision implies that there are alternative choices to be considered, and in such a case we want not only to identify as many of these alternatives as possible but to choose the one that best fits with our goals, objectives, desires, values, and so on (Harris, 1998).

Decision-making is a fundamental element of any sport. The managers of the Offices of Youth and Sports are part of decision-making processes in sports and play a significant role in the development of Professional Sports in the country; as such it seems the analysis of their decision-making styles would have a significant importance in the better guidance of the country's sports toward professionalism. As the sport moves toward professionalism, it requires better and stronger decisions; as a result, sport administrators (managers) need to have the required skills in different situations to guide their organizations effectively and responsibly with appropriate and correct decisions. Decision making is considered one of the inseparable parts of management and is manifested in each task of management (Benaret *et al.*, 2013).

Methods

Design of The Study

In this study the researcher used comparative research design specifically, Cross sectional design i.e., the researcher investigated whether there was a significant difference between the governmental and non-governmental bodies in youth and sport office of Mekelle and central zones on their

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time management skill and decision-making skill. In addition, the researcher was collected data from the selected respondents' one times using questionnaire and interview.

STUDY AREA

The study was conducted in the youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central zone in Tigray region.

Mekelle or Meqele, is the capital city in the northern [Tigray Region](#) of [Ethiopia](#). It is located around 780 kilometers north of the Ethiopian capital [Addis Ababa](#), at a latitude and longitude of $13^{\circ}29'N$ $39^{\circ}28'E$ [Coordinates](#): $13^{\circ}29'N$ $39^{\circ}28'E$, with an elevation of 2084 meters above sea level. Administratively, Mek'ele is considered a Special Zone, which is divided into seven [sub-cities](#). These are Addi Hak'i (ዓዲ ሓቂ, also spelled Addi Haqi in English), Ayder (ዓይደር), Haddinet (ሓደነት), Hawelti (ሓወልቲ), Qadamay Weyyane (ቀዳማይ ወያነ), Kwiha (ክዉሓ), and Semien (ሰሜን). This places the city in between the Addis Ababa

and [Dire Dawa](#) chartered cities (*astedader akabibi*, equivalent to a [kilib](#)), as well as the [Axum](#) and [Adigrat woredas](#). The city is an economic, cultural, and political hub in the Northern region of the country.

Mehakelegnaw (or "The central [Zone]") is a Zone in the [Ethiopian Region](#) of [Tigray](#). Mehakelegnaw is bordered on the east by [Misraqawi \(Eastern\)](#), on the south by [Debub Misraqawi \(South Eastern\)](#), on the west by [Semien Mi'irabawi \(North Western\)](#) and on the north by [Eritrea](#). Towns and cities in Mehakelegnaw include [Axum](#) and [Adwa](#), as well as the historically significant village of [Yeha](#) and the town of Tembien Abiyi Adi.

In this study the researcher selected ten Woreda and Sub-city youth and sport offices i.e. five Sub-cities (Ayder, Hawelti, K/Weyane, Kuha, and Adihaki) from Mekelle Zone and five Woreda (L/Maychew, T/Maychew, Axum, Adwa and AdiAhferom) youth and sport offices were selected from Central Zone.

Figure1. Location map of the study area

Selection of Subjects

In this study, the researcher selected ten Woredas /Sub-city youth and sport offices from the total of-19-Woredas and Sub-cities i.e., five out of the seven youth and sport offices from Mekelle zone and five out of the twelve youth and sport offices from Central zone of Tigray region by a method of simple random sampling technique. The researcher also used purposive sampling technique to select all the population (108) as respondents from the ten selected Woredas and Sub-city youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central Zones. All of the samples were

participated willingly and voluntarily in this study.

Selection of Variables and Instruments

Based on the researchers experience and knowledge gained from different sources, the two variables of management skills such as time management skill and decision-making skill were considered as variables for the present study. In this study the researcher used *5 liker test* questionnaire and unstructured interview in order to collect concrete and relevant information about the above two variables.

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Data Collection Procedure

The researcher obtained a letter of cooperation from Mekelle university sport science department to the respondents. All the participants of the study were asked for their willingness and informed about the purpose of the study before the questionnaire distributed. Setting arrangement was applied in order to avoid cheating and collect correct data from the respondents. The questionnaire was distributed in a face-to-face manner. Moreover, during the administration of the questionnaires further clarification was given wherever it was needed. The questionnaire was distributed and collected by the researcher after completion of them from expected respondents. In order to collect relevant information that helps the researcher to support/ triangulate the data that were collected by using questionnaire, the researcher was forwarded unstructured questions to the selected 10-experts then the interviewees were justified about the questions raised by the interviewer based on their feeling.

All the questionnaires were standardized through experts and experienced persons in management field including language professionals to assure their validity. After

incorporating all the suggestions made by the experts and experienced persons in management and sport field including language professionals, the final questionnaire was prepared and subjected to further scrutiny by conducting a pilot study to ascertain its reliability. The two Woredas/Sub-city namely, Adihaki and T/maichow were selected randomly for the study. The data gathered for the pilot test were subjected to computer analysis using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) to determine the reliability coefficient of the questionnaire and also to ascertain whether the questionnaire used was appropriate for the study. The result of the test of reliability showed that Cranach Alpha coefficient of each variable were 0.642 and 0.845. Spiegel (1992), Stevens (1986) reported that, an instrument is considered reliable if it lies between 0 and 1 and the closer the calculated reliability coefficient is to 0, the less reliable is the instrument, and the closer it is to 1, the more reliable is the instrument.

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS; version 20.0) was used for the data analysis. It was chosen to use parametric statistical tools even though the

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data was primarily ordinal. This can be justified by the interval like character of the given data and the greater accuracy and powerfulness of the paramagnetic test is maintained (Doering and Hubbared, 1979). One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was applied to compare the time management skill and decision-making skill of youth and sport offices of Mekelle and central zone among the governmental and none governmental bodies. Post-Hoc LSD multiple comparison was used to identify the

differences between the various groups in the youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central zone in Tigrai. The result was expressed by mean \pm standard error of mean and also to show whether there was statistical significance difference among the various groups in the youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central zone in Tigrai, the researcher was used P (sig) value. The level of significance was set at 0.05 levels of confidences.

RESULTS

TABLE 1

Descriptive Statistics For The Presence Of Good Time Management Skill In Youth And Sport Offices Of Mekelle And Central Zone

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Interval For Mean	Confidence Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound	
Central Zone Governmental Bodies	20	4.15	.366	.082	3.98	4.32	4 5
Central Zone Non-Governmental Bodies	34	2.62	1.231	.21	2.19	3.05	1 5
Mekelle Zone Governmental Bodies	20	3.75	.967	.216	3.30	4.20	2 5
Mekelle Zone Non-Governmental Bodies	34	3.47	1.161	.199	3.07	3.88	1 5
Total	108	3.38	1.182	.114	3.15	3.61	1 5

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Table1 shows that the central zone governmental bodies, central zone nongovernmental bodies, Mekelle Zone government bodies, and Mekelle Zone nongovernment bodies’ means \pm SEM on time management skill were 4.15 ± 0.082 , $2.62\pm .211$, $3.75\pm .216$, and $3.38\pm .199$

respectively. This shows that as there was mean difference between the four groups. But to show whether the difference was significant or not the researcher used one way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

TABLE 2

Analysis Of Variance (Anova) For Difference among The Four Categories In The Youth And Sport Offices Of Mekelle And Central Zones In Their Time Management Skill

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P(Sig.)
Between Groups	34.635	3	11.545		
Within Groups	114.800	104	1.104	10.459	.000
Total	149.435	107			

[F (2,172) =2.60(P>0.05)]

The result of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) revealed significant difference among the four categories in youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central zone in their time management skill.

in Mekelle zone had good time management skill except some committees. In the same manner most of the interviewees (80%) in the youth and sport offices of Central Zone responded that, the governmental bodies had good time management skill but the nongovernmental bodies were not using their time efficiently because they are working voluntarily without any salary.

This is occasioned by the fact that the calculated sig. (P) value of 0.000 was less than 0.05, level of significance. Based on the data collected using interview, 100% of the interviewees responded that as almost all staff members of the youth and sport offices

In order to identify among which group was the significance difference, the researcher

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used Post-Hoc LSD multiple comparison test.

TABLE 3

Post-Hoc Lsd Multiple Comparisons Test For The Difference Among The Various Groups In Youth And Sport Offices Of Mekelle And Central Zone In Their Time Management Skill.

		(J) Job designation between and within zones of respondent groups	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P (Sig).	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CZGB	CZNGB		1.532*	.296	.000	.95	2.12
	MZGB		.400	.332	.231	-.26	1.06
	MZNGB		.679*	.296	.024	.09	1.27
CZNGB	CZGB		-1.532*	.296	.000	-2.12	-.95
	MZGB		-1.132*	.296	.000	-1.72	-.55
	MZNGB		-.853*	.255	.001	-1.36	-.35
MZGB	CZGB		-.400	.332	.231	-1.06	.26
	CZNGB		1.132*	.296	.000	.55	1.72
	MZNGB		.279	.296	.347	-.31	.87
MZNGB	CZGB		-.679*	.296	.024	-1.27	-.09
	CZNGB		.853*	.255	.001	.35	1.36
	MZGB		-.279	.296	.347	-.87	.31

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

CZGB-Central Zone governmental bodies, CZNGB-Central Zone nongovernmental bodies, MZGB-Mekelle Zone governmental bodies, MZNGB-Mekelle Zone nongovernmental bodies

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P-value needed for significance at 0.05-level of significance.

Based on the multiple comparison (pair wise) of the mean score of the four categories of respondents, there was statistically significant difference among the Central Zone governmental bodies and Central Zone nongovernmental bodies in their time management skill because the calculated (P) Value of 0.000 was less than 0.05- level of significance.

In the same vein there was statistically significant difference between the mean score of Central Zone governmental bodies and Mekelle Zone non-governmental bodies in their time management skill because the calculated (P) value of 0.024 was less than 0.05- level of significance.

However, there was no statistically significant difference between Central Zone governmental bodies and Mekelle Zone governmental bodies because the calculated

(P) value of 0.231 was greater than 0.05-level of significance.

There was statistically significant difference between the mean score of Central Zone nongovernmental bodies and Mekelle Zone governmental bodies in their time management skill because the calculated (P) value of 0.000 was less than 0.05- level of significance and also there was statistically significant difference between the mean score of Central Zone nongovernmental bodies and Mekelle Zone nongovernmental bodies since the calculated (P) value of .001 was less than 0.05 level of significance.

There was no statistically significant difference between the mean score of Mekelle Zone governmental bodies and Mekelle Zone nongovernmental bodies in their time management skill because the calculated (P) value of 0.347 was greater than 0.05- level of significance.

FIGURE 1

Graphical Comparison On Time Management Skills Between The Four Groups In The Youth And Sport Offices Of Mekelle And Central Zone.

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TABLE 4,
Descriptive Statistics for the Presence Of Good Decision-Making Skill In Youth And Sport Offices
Of Mekelle And Central Zone

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Min	Max
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
central zone governmental bodies	20	4.30	.470	.105	4.08	4.52	4	5
Central zone non-governmental bodies	34	2.82	1.242	.213	2.39	3.26	1	5
Mekelle zone governmental bodies	20	3.85	.875	.196	3.44	4.26	2	5
Mekelle zone non-governmental bodies	34	3.79	.914	.157	3.48	4.11	2	5
Total	108	3.59	1.103	.106	3.38	3.80	1	5

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Table 4 Shows that the central zone governmental bodies', central zone non-governmental bodies, Mekelle Zone government bodies, and Mekelle Zone non-government bodies means± SEM on decision making skill were 4.30± 0.105, 2.82±0.213, 3.85±0.196, and 3.79±0.157 respectively. This indicates that as there was

TABLE 5,

Analysis Of Variance (Anova) For Difference Among The Four Categories In The Youth And Sport Offices Of Mekelle And Central Zones In Their Decision-Making Skill

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P(Sig.)
Between Groups	28.946	3	9.649		
Within Groups	101.600	104	.977	9.877	.000
Total	130.546	107			

[F (2,172) =2.60(P>0.05)]

The result of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) in the above shows that a significant difference among the four categories in youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central zone in their decision-making skill. This is occasioned by the fact that the calculated sig. (P) value of 0.000 was less than 0.05, level of significance. In addition, the data collected by using interview showed that as there was good

mean difference between the four groups in the youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central zone. But to show whether the difference was significant or not the researcher used one way analysis of variance (ANOVA).

decision-making skill in the youth and sport offices of both Mekelle and Central Zone. Since 80% of the interviewees in both Mekelle and Central Zone responded as most of the staffs have good decision making skill. In order to identify among which group was the significance difference the researcher used Post-Hoc LSD multiple comparison test.

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TABLE 4.7.2

Post-Hoc Lsd Multiple Comparisons Test For The Difference Among The Various Groups In Youth And Sport Offices of Mekelle And Central Zone In Their Decision-Making Skill

S(I) Job designation between and within zones of respondent groups	Job (J) designation between and within zones of respondent groups	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P (Sig).	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
CZGB	CZNGB	1.326*	.279	.000	.77	1.88
	MZGB	.300	.313	.339	-.32	.92
	MZNGB	.356	.279	.204	-.20	.91
CZNGB	CZGB	-1.326*	.279	.000	-1.88	-.77
	MZGB	-1.026*	.279	.000	-1.58	-.47
	MZNGB	-.971*	.240	.000	-1.45	-.50
MZGB	CZGB	-.300	.313	.339	-.92	.32
	CZNGB	1.026*	.279	.000	.47	1.58
	MZNGB	.056	.279	.841	-.50	.61
MZNGB	CZGB	-.356	.279	.204	-.91	.20
	CZNGB	.971*	.240	.000	.50	1.45
	MZGB	-.056	.279	.841	-.61	.50

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

CZGB-Central Zone governmental bodies, CZNGB-Central Zone nongovernmental bodies, MZGB-Mekelle Zone governmental bodies, MZNGB-Mekelle Zone nongovernmental bodies, P-value needed for significance at 0.05- level of significance.

Based on the above Post-Hoc LSD multiple comparison (pair wise) of the mean score of the four categories of respondents, there was

statistically significant difference between the means score of Central Zone governmental bodies and Central Zone non-

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governmental bodies in their decision-making skill because the calculated (P) Value of 0 .000 was less than 0.05- level of significance. However, there was no statistically significant difference between Central Zone governmental bodies and Mekelle Zone governmental bodies because the calculated (P) value of 0.339 was greater than 0.05- level of significance. In the same manner there was no statistically significant difference between the mean score of Central Zone governmental bodies and Mekelle Zone nongovernmental bodies because the calculated (P) value of 0.204 was greater than 0.05- level of significance. There was statistically significant difference between the mean score of Central Zone nongovernmental bodies and Mekelle Zone governmental bodies in their decision-

making skill because the calculated (P) value of 0.000 was less than 0.05- level of significance and also Central zone nongovernmental bodies had 1.026 less mean score than Mekelle zone governmental bodies. In the same vein there was statistically significant difference between the mean score of Central Zone nongovernmental bodies and Mekelle Zone nongovernmental bodies since the calculated (P) value of .000 was less than 0.05, level of significance. There was no statistically significant difference between Mekelle Zone governmental bodies and Mekelle Zone nongovernmental bodies in their decision-making skill because the calculated (P) value of 0.841 was greater than 0.05- level of significance.

FIGURE-2, Graphical Comparison On Decision Making Skill Between The Four Groups In The Youth And Sport Offices Of Mekelle And Central Zone

DISCUSSION

The purpose of the study was to compare the time management skill and decision-making skill in the youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central Zone. The results and findings of the study showed statistically significant difference among the governmental bodies and nongovernmental bodies in the youth and sport offices of Mekelle and central zones in relation to their time management skill. The Post-Hoc LSD multiple comparisons shows that Central Zone governmental bodies scored significantly better result in time management skill than Central Zone nongovernmental bodies and Mekelle Zone

nongovernmental bodies since the calculated p-value was less than the p-tabulated value. In the same manner Mekelle Zone governmental and nongovernmental bodies showed significantly better time management skill than Central Zone non-governmental bodies. However, there was no significance difference between Mekelle and Central Zone governmental bodies in time management since the calculated p-value was greater than the p-tabulated value. In addition, there was no significance difference between Mekelle Zone governmental and nongovernmental bodies in time management. The findings of the study were

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in agreement/in line with the study of Michael and Olasunkanmi (2015) conducted research on the time management and administrative effectiveness and concluded that, a well-managed time have high significant relationship with organizational goals achievement and aid administrative effectiveness of any organizations. This study was also supported by Orgenstern (2007) concluded that, time management is a factor in solving organizational problems and he believes that the efficient use of time causes the person with perfect vision can look deeper into the issues and try to solve them. In this study statistically significance difference was found among the governmental bodies and nongovernmental bodies in the youth and sport offices of Mekelle and Central zones in relation to their decision-making skill. The Post-Hoc LSD multiple comparisons shows that, Central Zone nongovernmental bodies showed less significant result when compared to Mekelle and Central Zone governmental bodies and Mekelle Zone nongovernmental bodies in decision making skill since the calculated p-value was less than the p-tabulated value. However, there was no significant difference between Mekelle and Central Zone governmental bodies and Mekelle Zone

nongovernmental bodies in decision making skill since the calculated p-value was greater than the p-tabulated value. The data collected by using interview showed that as there was good decision-making skill in the youth and sport offices of both Mekelle and Central Zone. Since 80% of the interviewees in both Mekelle and Central Zone responded as most of the staffs had good decision-making skill. The result and finding of this study were supported by Bibi Asia *et al.* (2013) conducted a study on the Decision-Making Practices in the Universities of Pakistan and concluded that, decision making is the worthy and integral element of management process and influences organizational setup.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis of the data, interpretation of results and discussion of findings the following conclusions were made.

1. Both Mekelle and Central Zone governmental bodies have good time management skill. However, Central Zone non-governmental bodies have extremely poor time management skill when compared to Mekelle zone non-governmental bodies.
2. Mekelle and Central Zone governmental bodies have good decision-making skill and also there was no significant difference

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among those two groups. However, Mekelle zone non-governmental bodies have better decision-making skill when compared to Central Zone non-governmental bodies.

Recommendation:

Based on the above results and conclusions the researcher recommended that, the non-governmental bodies in the youth and sport offices of central zone should improve their time management skill and decision-making skill.

The government should allow enough accommodation and all necessary payment to the non-governmental bodies in order to use their time wisely and efficiently.

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